

(AP) and 1590 cm^{-1} (AMP) splits into two bands and shifts to higher wave number by $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating that one of pyrimidine nitrogen is associated in bonding to copper(II) atom¹³.

The ir spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})(\text{ONO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1368 , $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1165 and 1140 and $\delta(\text{ONO})$ at 820 cm^{-1} . The unusual lowering of $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ in complex suggests oxygen bonding of NO_2 group in $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})(\text{ONO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The ir spectra of nitrate complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays ν_{NO_3} stretch at 1478 , 1278 and 1015 cm^{-1} which are characteristic frequencies of unidentate nitrate group¹⁴. The ir spectra of sulphato complex $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exhibits ν_{SO} at 1130 and 1030 (ν_{s} split) and 970 cm^{-1} (ν_1). The splitting of ν_{s} band indicates monocoordination of SO_4^{2-} group in $\text{Cu}(\text{AP})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex¹⁵. All the hydrated complexes display a broad and strong absorption near 3450 cm^{-1} due to water molecule. The $\rho_{\text{OH}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ could not be located near $680\text{--}85\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating absence of coordination of H_2O in the hydrated complexes¹⁴. Thus, from ir spectral studies, it is inferred that anions are coordinated and amino as well as one of pyrimidine ring nitrogen of the ligand are involved in bonding, probably as bridging group in complexes.

References

1. A. M. MICHELSON, "The Chemistry Nucleosides and Nucleotides", Academic, New York, 1963, p. 20.
2. M. GRUNBERG-MANAGO, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1962, 31, 301.
3. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS in "Modern Coordination Chemistry", eds. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 403.
4. D. G. BREWER and P. T. T. WONG, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1966, 44, 1407.
5. W. E. HATFIELD and R. WHYMAN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1969, 5, 47.
6. W. R. MCWHINNIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2959.
7. J. FERGUSON and B. O. WEST, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1966, 1569.
8. D. M. L. GOODGAME and F. A. COTTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2298; A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic and Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amstardam, 1968, Chap. 9.
9. L. SACCONI and M. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 278.
10. J. FERGUSON and B. O. WEST, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1966, 1599.
11. L. L. FUNK and T. R. ORTOLAND, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 567.
12. T. R. HARKING, J. L. WALTER, O. E. HARRIS and H. FRFISER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 260.
13. B. C. CURRAN, D. N. SEN, S. MIZUSHIMA and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 429.
14. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1967, pp. 173, 167, 164.
15. B. M. GATEHOUSE, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4222.

Palladium(II) Complexes of some α -Oximinobenzoyl-acetarylamide Semicarbazones and Thiosemicarbazones

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THE present paper deals with the preparation and characterisation of palladium(II) complexes with the following α -oximinobenzoylacetarylamide semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones:

where, X=O (semicarbazone); X=S (thiosemicarbazone); R=H (α -oximinobenzoylacetylanilide), *o*-CH₃ or *p*-CH₃ (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-*o/p*-toluidide), *o*-Cl or *p*-Cl (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-*o/p*-chloroanilide), *o*-OCH₃ (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-*o*-aniside), and 2,4-(CH₃)₂ (α -oximinobenzoylacetyl-2,4-xylidide).

Experimental

Aqueous solution of Pd²⁺ chloride (Johnson Matthey) (0.05 M; 10 ml) was gradually added to ethanolic solution (2%; 25 ml) of α -oximinobenzoylacetylanilide semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone and acidified with dilute HCl. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and digested on a steam-bath for 0.5 h. The precipitates separated were filtered, washed with hot water and aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) and dried in an oven at 110°. The Pd²⁺ chelates of the other α -oximinobenzoylacetarylamide semicarbazones/thiosemicarbazones of the series were prepared in the same manner. The complexes were bright yellow to golden yellow in colour and decomposed at $\approx 290^\circ$. Analytical data are given in Table 1.

Infrared spectra (KBr) of the ligands and complexes were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss UR-10 spectrophotometer fitted with LiF, NaCl and KBr prisms. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the finely powdered chelates were measured on a Beckman DU-10 spectrometer fitted with reflectance attachment, magnesium oxide being used as a reference material.

Results and Discussion

In ir spectra, of the ligands, the ν_{OH} band appears around $2800\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the

presence of intramolecular H-bond in the ligands¹. The absence of this ν_{O-H} ligand band in ir spectra of the Pd^{II} complexes gave an indication of the

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Pd^{II} COMPLEXES OF α -OXIMINO BENZOYLACETARYLAMIDE SEMICARBAZONES AND THIOSEMICARBAZONES

R	Compd.	Analysis % :	
		Found	(Calcd.)
H	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃) ₂	14.28	18.72
		(14.30)	(18.55)
o-CH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃) ₂	13.68	18.08
		(13.63)	(17.88)
o-Cl	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₆ O ₃ Cl) ₂	13.25	17.16
		(12.95)	(16.99)
o-OCH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃) ₂	13.39	17.26
		(13.09)	(17.18)
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Pd(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃) ₂	13.58	17.45
		(13.16)	(17.27)
H	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃ S) ₂	13.88	18.12
		(13.56)	(17.79)
p-CH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S) ₂	13.61	17.36
		(13.33)	(17.18)
p-Cl	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₆ O ₃ S) ₂	12.70	16.58
		(12.46)	(16.36)
o-OCH ₃	Pd(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S) ₂	12.48	16.55
		(12.60)	(16.53)
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Pd(C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S) ₂	12.71	16.76
		(12.66)	(16.61)

replacement of hydrogen of the oximino group by the metal. The shift of ν_{NO} ligand band from 940–970 to 1 150–1 180 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicated the coordination through N and not through O of oximino group, and the complexes contained the nitron (N→O) linkage which is known to absorb at about 1 200 cm⁻¹ as a very strong band². Such shift of ν_{NO} ligand from about 1 000 to about 1 200 cm⁻¹ showed the nitronic type linkage in many oxime complexes³⁻⁵. The strong band around 1 595–1 640 cm⁻¹ in the ligands was assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ ⁶; in the complexes, this band appeared around 1 560–1 590 cm⁻¹. The lowering of $\nu_{C=N}$ indicated coordination of 1-N of the semicarbazide/thiosemicarbazide moiety. The ν_{N-N} ligand band around 1 010–1 040 cm⁻¹ shifted to higher frequency in the chelates by 25–40 cm⁻¹ indicating the monodentate linkage of N–N residue⁷. The presence of C=S bands at 800–860 and 1 040–1 090 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands as well as in chelates suggested non-involvement of this group in coordination of the metal⁸. The ligands therefore acted in a bidentate manners and not as a tridentate one. The infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes revealed bands around 3 300, 3 100 and 3 400 cm⁻¹, indicating secondary association, primary association and free N–H vibrations of amides, respectively⁹. The strong bands in the ligands and complexes around 1 650, 1 540 and 1 300 cm⁻¹ are attributed to amide I, II and III, respectively⁹.

The electronic (reflectance) spectra of these complexes exhibit two bands. One broad band (in some cases a shoulder) was observed in the range

520–585 nm (19 231–17 094 cm⁻¹) and the second and more intense band was observed in the range 375–410 nm (26 667–24 390 cm⁻¹), which may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively. The band positions are in agreement with those generally observed for square-planar Pd^{II} complexes^{10,11}. All the Pd^{II} complexes were found to be diamagnetic.

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References

1. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Nankodo, Tokyo, 1964 p. 167.
2. P. A. S. SMITH and J. E. ROBERTSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 1197.
3. R. BLINK and D. HADZI *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4536.
4. A. CHAKRAVORTY and K. C. KALIA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 2016.
5. K. BURGER, I. RUFF and F. RUFF, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 179.
6. H. STERK and E. ZIEGLER, *Monatsch. Chem.*, 1966, 97, 1131.
7. A. BRATBANTI, F. DALLVALLE and M. A. PALLINGHELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1430.
8. D. M. WILES, B. A. GINGRAS and T. SUPRUNCHEK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 869.
9. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Nankodo, Tokyo, 1964, p. 45.
10. M. BIDDAU, M. MASSACESI, G. RONTICELLI, G. DEVOTO and I. A. ZAKHAROVA, *Polyhedron*, 1983, 1261.
11. JAI SINGH and S. P. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 710.

Complexes of Dioxouranium(II) and Thorium(IV) with Potentially Tetradentate Schiff Bases

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IN the present communication, we report the synthesis and spectral properties of a few uranium(VI) and thorium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases,

R = H, OCH₃